

A Study of the Aesthetics of Translation Using Functional Equivalence Theory

Nasiba Atabaeva^{1*}

¹ College of Foreign Languages and Arts, Taiyuan University of Technology

Abstract: Functional equivalence theory is a dynamic equivalence theory that emphasizes the expression and meaning of the source language, with meaning being more important than form. Long-term aesthetic requirements for translation can be divided into three types of progressive beauty: beauty in form and sound, beauty in structure, and beauty in meaning. The meaning comes first, followed by the sound and form. The focus of this article is the comparison of theory and aesthetics, or the exploration of aesthetics based on theory, to investigate the unique application of its theory to the aesthetics of translation, compare its differences from general translation, where beauty lies, and how to resonate with both source and target language readers.

Keywords: Functional equivalence theory; Aesthetics; Resonance

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 11 June, 2023; **Published:** 17 June, 2023

How to cite this article: Nasiba Atabaeva (2023). *A Study of the Aesthetics of Translation Using Functional Equivalence Theory*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(6), 57-62. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8051117>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1.Introduction

1.1 Translation

Translation is defined as "an act of information transformation and dissemination, i.e., the construction of a language bridge to transform one type of speech information into another." And his birth was predetermined from the beginning of language creation, with various civilizations, regional cultures, and historical origins destined for the emergence and development of various languages. The act of "translation" gradually emerged to facilitate communication between people speaking different languages.

The intersection of translation and aesthetics can be traced back to the early AD translation of Buddhist scriptures. People are constantly seeking beauty, and the term "beauty" has a long history in China, beginning with the image in Shang oracle bone inscriptions, beginning with the surface. People's constant pursuit gradually transforms from concrete to abstract over time, hiding in the depths of time and externalizing in various forms. On the path of translation, people still follow an ancient habit: the search for beauty, which is people's thirst for ideal forms, in the hope that "beauty" can be displayed in front of the world. As a result, the requirements for translation aesthetics have been changing and evolving for thousands of years. Many discussions and studies on "essence" and "essence" have been conducted, from the old translation school represented by the true meaning of Buddhist scriptures translation to the new translation school represented by Xuanzang's "existential essence" theory, and the exploration and progression of

beauty. As a result, many translation aesthetic theories that have influenced Chinese traditional translation have gradually emerged, such as Ma Jianzhong's late Qing Dynasty theory of good translation, Yan Fu's theory of faithfulness, expressiveness, and elegance, which has had the most profound impact on Chinese translation circles, and even the self translation theory summarized by modern Mr. Xu Yuanchong: The art of beautification, creating excellence, is like a competition that reveals the realm of translation's three beauties - beauty of sound, beauty of form, and beauty of beautiful meaning. This is all part of a gradual pursuit of translation aesthetics. Beauty is manifested in meaning, externalized in form, manifested in sound, and combined with both spirit and form, ultimately achieving a magnificent realm, as a result of thousands of years of culture and the exploration of countless ancestors. This is the ideal translation aesthetic goal, as well as the stunning effect of the best translation. In reality, covering all aspects may be difficult, so translation aesthetics can be divided into three levels: beauty in form and sound, beauty in structure, and beauty in meaning. The goal is to achieve a profound meaning, which is a gradual deepening process from the outside to the inside and from the outside to the inside. This necessitates going beyond formal closeness or similarity in content and gradually approaching the original meaning of the source language and the ultimate realm of beauty.

1.2 Functional equivalence theory

The theory of functional equivalence seeks to achieve meaning consistency. It seeks functional equivalence between the source and target languages rather than rigid correspondence on the surface of words, which is the core of this theory known as "functional equivalence." Eugene Nida, a well-known American translation theorist, proposed it first from the standpoint of linguistics and the nature of translation. This was a significant breakthrough in existing translation theories at the time, offering a new perspective to the domestic and international translation communities. It temporarily abandoned debate and research on open source Chinese texts and target language texts in favor of pursuing readers' feelings or higher level translation beauty. Nida classified the translation practice process into three stages: analysis, transformation, and reorganization. Material replacement is required, just as it is with a wooden bicycle that must be converted into an aluminum alloy bicycle. However, despite its apparent simplicity, many considerations are required, with each component carefully considered. First, it is necessary to analyze and comprehend the benefits and drawbacks of the two materials, as well as fully comprehend the basic structure and purpose of the bicycle by disassembling the original wooden bicycle, that is, to analyze and disassemble the information disclosed by the source language book, such as the characteristics of Language construct, cultural background, the author's intention and external influence, comprehend the details, and comprehend the connotation. Internalize source language text analysis into a basic framework that anyone can use; Second, we should look for aluminum alloy products that can be replaced but not replicated one-to-one. To carry out a feasible replacement, we should consider the characteristics of the two materials, that is, to transform the source language text structure to the target language text structure, such as language construct, grammatical forms, cultural differences and similarities between the two sides, but not rigid structure or single word meaning correspondence, but based on the structural framework of the two languages, different cultural characteristics, Identify vocabulary, architecture, or concepts that can be transformed using a thorough understanding of the intended text. It is the best if not the correct, while appropriate and expressive expressions are essential. Finally, the transformation of wooden bicycles to aluminum alloy bicycles will be completed, resulting in a new material that is equally or more convenient for bicycle transportation. This means that a comprehensive restructuring will be carried out, taking into account all aspects, and with a clear plan, the known source language text will be transformed into a restructured target language text, so that the target language text can achieve an approximate understanding of semantics and readers' senses with the source language text, thus achieving functional equivalence. Its theory is primarily based on the culture of the source language, with the goal of breaking down barriers between languages, bridging cultural gaps, and eliminating cultural differences between the source language and the target language, and seeking the resonance of meaning between source language text readers and target language text readers. Allow readers of the target language text to feel the same or similar emotions as readers of the source language text, through emotional

resonance. This is also an important example of translation aesthetics. Meaning comes first, form comes second," which means that, in addition to the most basic expression of meaning, translation aesthetics should rise to a higher level, seeking equality, resonance, and empathy. The highest realm pursued by functional equivalence is the cultural and emotional resonance achieved by the vast stars spanning history between different languages, and it is also the ideal realm of translation aesthetics that translators have been steadfast in their pursuit throughout history. As a result, language translation, according to the theory of functional equivalence, has its own aesthetic implications or a pace comparable to the pursuit of aesthetics. This gives birth to beauty and wonder, which complement each other like fish in water.

2. Smart translation of sentences

In English, consider the famous palindrome "Able was I ere I saw El ba." This sentence is attributed to Napoleon, Emperor of the First French Empire, who was forced to abdicate after the bloody Rhine War in 1841 and exiled to Elba Island. "Able" is generally capable and capable in the source language semantics. According to the context, "invincible" can be translated in this sentence, while "ere" is an Old English word that is consistent with the word "before" in Modern English, which means "before." As a result, based on the specific meaning of each word, this sentence can be translated literally as "I was invincible before I saw Elba." However, for the literal translation of this sentence, although the meaning of the sentence has a more correct translation and interpretation, so that the target readers can basically understand the surface meaning of the source language, it is only to achieve the meaning, and the unique beauty inherent in the source language cannot be empathized with the translated readers through this literal translation. A close examination of the source language sentence reveals its unique sentence structure - palindrome - which ensures that the entire sentence is basically consistent from pronunciation to writing, whether forward or backward, presenting a distinct charm of palindrome beauty. Concise and to-the-point, with far-reaching implications. This is what Napoleon said when he first experienced a great failure in life and was forced to be exiled for the first time, based on an analysis of his creative background as well as the state or intention presented in his language. Imagine an invincible emperor meeting such a significant Waterloo for the first time in his life, and losing everything he had already gained. I was invincible before Elba saw me, just like the implied meaning of the source language when read from right to left. As a result, Elba represents not only an island, but also a significant symbol of Napoleon's defeat. An island, on the other hand, implies a pun, which is the unyielding and proud cry of a great monarch. It also implies his refusal to do so, as well as his determination and cry to recast glory, and history has provided the answer, which can be explored through his subsequent rise to power. Through a unique writing style between the lines, the source language sentence, composed of only a few words, exudes a unique charm with profound meaning. This is also a beauty that the literal translation above cannot convey.

Mr. Ma Hongjun's translation of "Lost Island, Lost Alone." is, on the other hand, a typical functional equivalence translation, skillfully utilizing the three major steps of analysis, transformation, and reorganization. Based on the historical context of Napoleon's failed exile in the source language sentence, the author accurately analyzes the syntactic structure of the source language sentence, the speaker's intentions, and the similarities and differences with the target language culture, language structure, grammatical forms, and so on, adopts literary rhetoric forms consistent with the source language sentence, and deftly converts the source language vocabulary and the target language vocabulary. Simply put, the writing style and grammatical structure are not only relative to the source language sentence, but they are also all very rigorous palindromes, with appropriate forms, beautiful shapes, rhymes, and structures. They also achieve functional equivalence in meaning and a certain level of meaning beauty. Looking at it more closely, starting with the transformation of source language sentences, transforming Napoleon's self-proclaimed "I" into "solitary" in the source language sentences is an extremely clever step that serves as the foundation of the cultural bridge between the two sides. "Gu" is the self-proclaimed name of ancient kings in Chinese culture. This transformation not only conforms to Napoleon's image status in the source language, but also allows translated readers to accurately concretize the

characters in the source language and understand the source language culture based on their own culture, resulting in a higher standard of cultural response. The two 'defeats' vividly demonstrate the source language sentence's connotation, one corresponding to the previous situation's all-powerful life slide, and the other corresponding to the implied meaning of 'Elba' in the source language sentence. While ensuring structure neatness and alignment, it sublimates emotions repeatedly, achieving emotional resonance and communication between source language readers and target language readers, and even sublimation of understanding in the target language culture. Translation is said to be very natural and clever.

3. Smart Translation of Place Names

Using the term 'Utopia' as an example, its original meaning is 'nowhere' or 'good place', and its meaning can also be extended to 'ideal perfection' or 'impossible good thing'. These straightforward translations are sufficient to make people understand their surface meaning if translated according to their original meaning, but they are also somewhat confusing. The question is, what is this exactly? "Utopia" is the final Chinese translation. This translation, on the one hand, is a transliteration of the source language's English pronunciation, with the beauty of the line sound contained in the source language; on the other hand, the Chinese translation is analyzed from the perspective of text composition, based on an understanding of the transformation between the target language culture and the source language culture. The three characters of "utopia" are explained from the target language's perspective: "wu" represents "no," "tuo" contains "sustenance," and "bang" means "country" and "city-state." As a result, the utopian country is the translated meaning of the three characters of utopia. The 'ideal country' is a yearning for ideals, a presence that is both achievable and unattainable, like a beautiful vision. This corresponds to the source language's semantic meaning, achieving functional equivalence while allowing translated readers to immediately understand the content and meaning of the source language semantics from their own culture, and even appreciate the emotional resonance brought about by cultural extension. The three words 'utopian' will make translated text readers feel like they are touching an ideal picture that is irresistibly captivating, rather than concretizing a free and beautiful dream that can be followed. This is the image that the source language semantics were intended to convey, allowing translated text readers to fully empathize with the source language readers' feelings. They can feel the concretized source language connotation from the translated text unconsciously, and they can even sublimate the source language connotation. Achieve implied beauty and emotional resonance to achieve a higher level of emotional communication. "Translation," Nida once said, "is the use of the closest and most natural equivalent language to reproduce the information of the source language in the target language." This is the ideal translation situation, the highest level of functional equivalence, and the ideal manifestation of translation beauty.

Similarly, most Chinese people are familiar with the famous city of 'Fontainebleau' in Paris, France, thanks to its unique translation name. She is not only the "Fang Dan Bo Luo" described by the romantic poet Xu Zhimo, but also the "Fontainebleau" on Zhu Ziqing's Qing Jun paper. When compared to the translation of Xu and Zhu, the original meaning of "beautiful spring" appears to be inferior. If translated in this manner, it is also difficult to touch people's hearts, far less than the stunning "Fang Dan Bo Luo" and "Fontainebleau." "Fangdan Boluo" and "Fontainebleau" are both dynamically equivalent to the source words. Listening to their sounds, they are formed from the pronunciation of the source language French and contain a certain phonological beauty. However, when comparing the two words, they decide that "Fangdan Boluo" is the best. Not only is it consistent with the sound and sound beauty of the source language in terms of sound and shape, but the beauty of "Fontainebleau" is beyond words and appears to be the incomparable beauty in dreams, according to the sense experience of the target language readers. The interweaving of cultures, the integration of structures, and the dynamic equivalence, for example, cause target language readers to unconsciously visualize the beautiful "Fontainebleau" landscape - the intersection of maple trees, birches, and other colors, for example. Layers of red and white are combined. The sun is shining brightly. The description of color and scenery alone transports people into a beautiful picture shared by all five senses, causing endless reverie. Its beauty is meaningful, profound,

and unforgettable, and it enchants people. The emotion is intense. Although "Fangdan Boluo" is more beautiful than "Fontainebleau" in terms of travel sound, its structure and meaning are a little thin when compared to "Fontainebleau," as if beauty has limits. As a result, "Fontainebleau" brings the target language readers' understanding of "Fontainebleau's" beauty closer to the source language readers' feelings of its beauty, allowing them to derive more meaning from their own language and culture while sympathizing with the source language. This is the source of its allure.

4. Conclusion

The transmission of beauty and the charm of language is the fusion of culture and emotional connection. People's search for beauty is never-ending, and beauty is to language what water is to fishing, complementing and complementing each other. Language cannot block the resonance and resonance of emotions, and beauty has no boundaries. Both functional equivalence theory and translation aesthetics aim to build a better bridge between cultures, to break down barriers between cultural differences, to break down emotional barriers caused by vastly different language environments, and to achieve emotional dialogue and communication among people from different cultures and languages. Text is a tool for communication, a silent language; language is a special symbol of culture and a communication bridge. The origins of various civilizations, diverse regional cultures, and humanistic characteristics have resulted in the emergence of various languages and characters, similar to a small stream separating two civilizations. They intersect, split, and expand like the long river of history. Translation, on the other hand, seeks to construct a symbolic and interconnected small bridge between two slowly drifting civilizations, whereas translation aesthetics, founded on the theory of functional equivalence, seeks to build a more exquisite and sturdy bridge. One is like a cornerstone, while the other is like polishing, with the same goal in mind: beauty. It is the expression of natural emotions, not the beauty of hard concave shapes. It is based on language symbols, seeking emotional resonance between source language and target language readers, and being able to express the meaning of the source language sentence more appropriately and naturally to target language readers, allowing the translation to reach a higher standard.

References

- [1] De Waard, J. and Nida, E.A. (1986) *From One Language to Another: Functional Equivalence in Bible Translation*. Thomas Nelson Inc., Edinburgh.
- [2] Nida, E.A. and Taber, C.R. (1969) *The Theory and Practice of Translation*. E. J. Brill, Leiden.
- [3] Nida, E.A. (2001) *Language and Culture: Context in Translating*. Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press, Shanghai.
- [4] Wang Jianguo *Chinese English Translation Studies: Basic Theory and Practice* [M] Beijing: China Translation Publishing House, 2019
- [5] Wang Jianguo *A Hierarchical Study of Adaptation Factors in Chinese English Translation* [M]//Wang Jianguo *Pragmatic Life - Collected Works of Professor He Ziran's 80th Birthday Celebration* Beijing: Higher Education Press, 2016: 275-283
- [6] Wang Jianguo, how natural is it? Focus on the process or the result—— The Influence of Translator's Mother Tongue on English Translated Text [J] *Shanghai Translation*, 2014 (2): 7-12
- [7] Ye Yufei, Yu Xiao *Translation Research on Language Deviation under the Guidance of Functional Equivalence Theory: Taking Lu Xun's Novel "Divorce" as an Example* [J] *Drama House*, 2018 (31): 202-203+215
- [8] Wu Biyu, Wang Jianguo *Differences in Aesthetic Concepts between Chinese and English and Their Language Expressions* [J] *Journal of East China University of Science and Technology (Social Science Edition)*, 2017, 32 (2): 98-106+116
- [9] Zhang Xiqian *An Analysis of Two English Translations of "The Scream" from the Perspective of Nida's Functional Equivalence* [J] *Journal of Hubei University of Science and Technology*, 2016, 36 (2): 137-138+150

